

STOCHASTIC MODELLING OF THE SPATIALLY DISTRIBUTED VISCOELASTICITY OF SHORT FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES USING RANDOM FIELDS

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ABSTRACT

Short fiber-reinforced composites, such as Polybutylene Terephthalate with a fiber mass fraction of 30%, exhibit enhanced mechanical properties due to embedded reinforcing short fibers. However, the reinforcing fibers and hence the microstructural randomness cause pronounced spatially distributed viscoelastic behavior, resulting from microstructural randomness. This study presents a combined experimental and numerical investigation to model and analyze the local distribution of viscoelastic parameters in short fiber-reinforced composites, both at the microscale and component level. In the experimental context, the viscoelastic behavior of the material is characterized using tensile testing at the component level and nanoindentation at the microscale. These analyses reveal significant variability in the creep properties of fiber-reinforced specimens compared to those of unreinforced Polybutylene terephthalate. The numerical multiscale simulation is based on random fields, where the viscoelastic behavior is described through a generalized Maxwell model by using a Prony series representation. With this, a connection between the microscale and component level is established. Therefore, at the microscale, artificial microstructures are generated based on statistical descriptors of fiber geometry and orientation. The material properties of the homogenized material are obtained through numerical simulations that respect Hill's condition. In order to account for the stochastic nature resulting from the microstructure at the component level, spatially varying material parameters are represented via second-order Gaussian random fields, discretized using the Karhunen-Loève expansion. With the presented multiscale approach, the spatial randomness of the viscoelastic behavior is successfully incorporated into numerical simulations. The findings of the numerical simulation exhibited a robust alignment with the experimental data, thus providing additional support for its practical relevance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short Fiber-Reinforced Composites (SFRCs) are formed by combining two or more constituent materials during an injection molding process [2]. In this specific case, thermoplastic Polybutylene terephthalate (PBT) is generally used as the matrix, while short fibers are utilized to provide mechanical reinforcement, resulting in increased stiffness and strength. However, polymer-based composites, such as PBT GF30 (with 30% fiber mass fraction), exhibit time-dependent deformation under sustained mechanical loads, a phenomenon generally referred to as viscoelasticity. This behavior is primarily attributed to the viscoelastic nature of the polymer matrix [5]. Since PBT GF30 can be processed by injection molding, its applications are found in the automotive, aerospace, and electronics industries. For these applications, a precise characterization of viscoelastic behavior is essential for reliable performance prediction [9].

The generalized Maxwell model is a widely used approach to describe the viscoelastic response of SFRCs [13]. This model conceptualizes the behavior of the material using a network of springs and dashpots, respectively representing elastic and viscous effects [13]. Due to its standardized structure, the Maxwell model is implemented in most commercial Finite Element Method (FEM) software packages [1]. The numerical implementation is typically based on the representation of the Prony series [13].

Although the addition of short fibers enhances the mechanical properties of SFRCs, it also introduces a notable drawback, such as the spatial heterogeneity of mechanical properties at the component level [10]. This heterogeneity is derived from the microstructure of the material itself [4, 11], which is primarily influenced by the manufacturing process, such as mold injection [2]. During mold injection, variations in flow velocity and the resulting shear forces in the cross-section of the melt flow cause non-uniform microstructural characteristics [2]. Consequently, this results in spatially distributed mechanical properties at the microscale and component levels.

The probabilistic nature of the microstructure is characterized by probability density functions of fiber length, fiber diameter, and fiber orientation [4, 12]. Due to the considerable disparity in the length scales, where the fiber length is much smaller than the overall dimensions of the component, a multiscale approach is essential to accurately capture the mechanical behavior of the SFRCs at the component level [10].

One potential framework for modeling the spatial distribution of mechanical parameters is to utilize random fields, thereby allowing for the representation of the behavior of inhomogeneous materials at the component level [14]. The numerical discretization of these random fields is based on the Karhunen-Loève expansion [7]. In this work, a two-dimensional cross-section of a standardized tensile test specimen, conforming to DIN EN ISO 527-2 type 1A, is used within a numerical framework to model at the component level and in an experimental context. First, the entries of the anisotropic elasticity tensor are determined using an artificial microstructure, which is described in detail in [10, 12]. The artificial microstructure is generated based on the probabilistic characteristics of fiber length, fiber orientation, and fiber diameter. The numerical simulation at the microscale is conducted using linear elastic modeling for both the fibers and the matrix material. Finally, the component-level numerical results obtained using a second-order Gaussian random field are compared with the experimental tensile creep data.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Viscoelasticity effects are defined as a time-dependent deformation process that occurs under constant load and temperature conditions, involving both elastic and viscous contributions. This phenomenon is of particular significance in polymer-based materials, which exhibit viscoelastic behavior, combining time-independent elasticity with time-dependent viscous flow. Due to the heterogeneity of the material, these time-dependent mechanical properties are spatially distributed. To effectively capture and analyze this phenomenon, a probabilistic approach is necessary.

2.1 Viscoelasticity

Creep is a component of viscoelasticity, defined as the time-dependent deformation of a material under constant load and temperature. This phenomenon is commonly observed in polymer-based materials, which exhibit a combination of elastic and viscous behavior [13]. This behavior is often referred to as viscoelastic behavior. Creep deformation is generally understood to occur in three stages: primary, secondary, and tertiary creep, as demonstrated in Figure 1, which presents a schematic representation of the strain ϵ , as a function of time t .

As illustrated in Figure 1 the primary creep stage is characterized by a deceleration in the strain rate. It occurs immediately after stress application, with the initial strain $\epsilon(0)$ representing the elastic response. A constant strain rate marks the secondary creep stage and is crucial to evaluating long-term material behavior. This is usually the longest stage. In the tertiary creep stage, the strain accelerates rapidly, ultimately leading to material failure.

The total strain $\epsilon_{\text{total}}(t)$ over time of the specimen under constant loads, as schematically presented in Figure 1, can be expressed additively as

$$\epsilon(t) = \epsilon_{\text{total}}(t) = \epsilon_{\text{linear elastic}} + \epsilon_{\text{creep}}(t). \quad (1)$$

Here, $\epsilon_{\text{linear elastic}}$ represents the immediate strain response upon the application of stress, following Hooke's law for linear elasticity. This component remains constant over time and does not contribute to the time-dependent deformation behavior of the material. However, the creep deformation $\epsilon_{\text{creep}}(t)$ accounts for the viscoelastic deformation that evolves under sustained loading, including all three stages.

In this study, the focus is on the primary and secondary stages because capturing the tertiary stage is time-consuming and experimentally challenging.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the typical behavior of creep strain ε , which is divided into three distinct stages, while constant load σ and temperature T are applied to a sample.

The mathematical models are derived using rheological elements that describe the stress-strain relations for the viscoelastic behavior [13]. These elements are depicted in Figure 2, where the spring element represents Hooke's law with stiffness K_{eq} . According to Newton's law, a dashpot is defined as a purely viscous material characterized by its dynamic viscosity, denoted by η . When the spring and dashpot are connected in series, it is referred to as the Maxwell element. Furthermore, by employing a parallelization approach with the N_i -th Maxwell elements and the equilibrium spring K_{eq} , the concept of the generalized Maxwell model is introduced.

Figure 2: Representation of rheological elements to describe viscoelasticity: a) a spring with the stiffness K_{eq} following Hooke's law, b) a dashpot representing purely viscous behavior, c) a Maxwell element consisting of a spring and dashpot in series, and d) a generalized Maxwell model.

For the generalized Maxwell model with $K_{N_i} = 1$, as detailed in [13], the stress-strain relationship for viscoelastic materials is formulated as a differential equation

$$\frac{d\sigma(t)}{dt} + \frac{K_1}{\eta_1}\sigma(t) = (K_{eq} + K_1)\frac{d\varepsilon(t)}{dt} + \frac{K_{eq}K_1}{\eta_1}\varepsilon(t). \quad (2)$$

This differential equation models the viscoelastic response of complex materials, encompassing stress relaxation and creep behavior [13].

A commonly used approach to characterize the time-dependent viscoelastic response is the Prony

series, which can be derived by applying the Laplace transform to the differential formulation of the generalized Maxwell model [13], as demonstrated in Equation 2. The Prony series effectively describes the time-dependent deformation behavior of materials, expressed as [13]

$$K(t) = K_{eq} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} K_i e^{-t/\tau_i}. \quad (3)$$

The relaxation function $K(t)$ characterizes the time-dependent decrease in material stiffness due to viscoelastic effects. Each exponential term corresponds to a Maxwell element with a distinct relaxation time τ_i , which captures different rates of stiffness relaxation [13]. In practical applications, the parameters of the Prony series K_{eq} , K_i , and τ_i are determined by fitting the Prony series to experimental data. The fitting process typically involves applying optimization techniques to minimize the discrepancy between the model's predictions and observations [5, 8]. The result of this process is a viscoelastic model that is tailored to the material under investigation.

2.2 Karhunen-Loève expansion

2.2.1 Second-order Gaussian random field

Quantities that are derived from random experiments and governed by the rules of probability theory are known as random variables, denoted as $Z(\omega)$. In a mechanical context, specific material properties, such as Young's modulus, are not constant but instead vary due to natural heterogeneity uncertainty. A well-known approach to representing this distribution is the Gaussian distribution, which is characterized by its first two statistical moments and thereby defines the normal distribution [14]. The statistical moments are the expected value, μ , and the standard deviation, σ .

By extending the random variable $Z(\omega)$ to the spatial coordinates \mathbf{x} , over the defined domain, one speaks of a random field [14]

$$Z(x) = Z(\omega, \mathbf{x}). \quad (4)$$

A Gaussian random field is fully characterized by the mean value $\mu(\mathbf{x})$, the standard deviation $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$, and the dimensionless correlation coefficient $\rho(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)$ [6, 14]. The correlation coefficient is a measure of the relationship between two points, \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 , of a random field. When combined with the covariance, it can be expressed as

$$\rho_{12} = \rho_{Z_1, Z_2} = \frac{Cov[Z_1, Z_2]}{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}. \quad (5)$$

One speaks of the auto-correlation when Z_1 and Z_2 are from the same random field $Z(\mathbf{x})$. Otherwise, it involves cross-covariance and cross-correlation.

It is assumed that the random fields are homogeneous. This indicates that the mean value and the standard deviation are independent of spatial coordinates and thus remain constant over a realization [14]. Additionally, the correlation is translation-independent and is therefore described by relative coordinates ξ .

2.2.2 Karhunen-Loève expansion of Gaussian random field

The Karhunen-Loève (KL) expansion provides a comprehensive framework for representing second-order Gaussian stochastic random field, functioning as a probabilistic analog to the classical Fourier transform [7]. This expansion is expressed as follows

$$X(\omega, \mathbf{x}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sqrt{\lambda_n} \phi_n(\mathbf{x}) Z_n(\omega), \quad (6)$$

where $Z_n(\omega)$ is an uncorrelated random variable, and λ_n and $\phi_n(\mathbf{x})$ are eigenpairs of a Fredholm integral of second-order. This Fredholm integral of second-order is written as

$$\int_D Cov[Z_1, Z_2] \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_1) d\mathbf{x}_1 = \lambda_n \phi_n(\mathbf{x}_2). \quad (7)$$

Moreover, the correlation must be established before generating a random field. However, a closed solution is feasible only for a limited number of correlation functions and domain shapes. Consequently, numerical methods are necessary. Furthermore, the random field is divided into deterministic and stochastic components, which are represented as

$$\begin{aligned} Z(\omega, \mathbf{x}) &= \mu(\mathbf{x}) + \alpha(\omega, \mathbf{x}) \\ &= \mu + X(\omega, \mathbf{x}). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Here, the mean of the random field $\mu(\mathbf{x})$ represents the deterministic part of it, while $\alpha(\omega, \mathbf{x})$ represents the stochastic part with an expected value of zero.

For the numerical generation of random fields, the optimal linear estimation expansion method is employed, as introduced in [6]. First, the covariance matrix, denoted by \mathbf{C} , is calculated for the predefined and discretized two-dimensional shape using the triangular function. The two-dimensional model of the tensile test specimen is schematically illustrated in Figure 3. This step is expressed as

$$\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = \rho(\xi_1, \xi_2), \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{C} is a $N \times N$ symmetric positive semi-definite matrix.

Figure 3: Standard tensile test specimen featuring a two-dimensional model representation, illustrating the discretization points and the relative distance ξ between the points \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 are shown schematically. Furthermore, a numerically generated second-order Gaussian random field for this two-dimensional model is exemplified.

This leads to the eigenvalue problem

$$\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \phi_n = \lambda_n \phi_n, \quad (10)$$

where the eigenpair $(\lambda_n$ and $\phi_n(\mathbf{x}))$ are determined. Furthermore, the eigenpair is used for the M -th truncated random fields \hat{Z} .

$$\hat{Z}(\omega, \mathbf{x}) = \mu + \sum_{n=1}^M \sqrt{\lambda_n} \phi_n(\mathbf{x}) Z_n(\omega). \quad (11)$$

This approximation is referred to as the truncated Karhunen–Loève expansion. An exemplary representation of a second-order Gaussian random field is provided in Figure 3.

2.3 Multiscale modeling framework

A Representative Volume Element (RVE) is crucial for modeling heterogeneous materials, such as SFRCs. The RVE must be sufficiently large to capture the statistical features of the heterogeneity while remaining small enough to function as a material point at the component level and independent of the RVE size, as demonstrated schematically in Figure 4 a). In contrast, smaller domains that do not fully satisfy these criteria are referred to as Statistical Volume Elements (SVEs). The purpose of SVEs is to investigate the variability of effective properties resulting from microstructural randomness.

Figure 4: Representation of the definition of the scale $l \ll d \ll L$ based on a tensile test specimen: a) various unique microstructures at different positions at the component level, and b) numerically modeled artificial microstructure.

Using the numerically modeled artificial microstructure, as depicted in Figure 4 b), the material properties are determined by Hill's condition [3]

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \rangle = \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle : \langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \rangle. \quad (12)$$

The generation of this artificial microstructure, considering the probabilistic characteristics of fiber length, fiber diameter, and fiber orientation, as detailed in [10–12]. The properties of the materials used for the linear elastic model are summarized in Table 1.

	Fiber	PBT (Matrix)
Young's modulus	83.9 GPa	2.67 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.22	0.41
Density	2500 kg m ⁻³	1300 kg m ⁻³

Table 1: Fiber and PBT (matrix) material properties for modeling the artificial microstructure.

The effective material properties can be calculated by applying three independent load cases for each type of boundary condition, namely Dirichlet and Neumann types, to the numerical artificial microstructure. By averaging $\langle \cdot \rangle$ the properties calculated in the domain, the homogenized material properties are written as

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle = \mathbf{C}^{\text{eff}} : \langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \rangle \quad (13)$$

and

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \rangle = \mathbf{S}^{\text{eff}} : \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{C}^{eff} and \mathbf{S}^{eff} represent the effective stiffness and the compliance tensor, respectively. In the case of time-dependent behavior, the relation exemplarily for stiffness behavior is written as

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{t}) \rangle = \mathbf{C}^{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{t}) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0 \quad (15)$$

Here, only the matrix material is modeled as viscoelastic using a Prony series with a single branch, as shown in Figure 2, with $K_{Ni} = 1$. These Prony parameters, which were obtained through experimental means and are specific to unreinforced PBT, are listed in Table 2. This is achieved by fitting the experimental data with the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. The identified Prony parameters for PBT are applied exclusively to the matrix phase of the artificial microstructures, with the corresponding results shown in Figure 10 a) for five different microstructures. The five microstructures considered are subdomains (d) extracted from the larger volume (LB) shown in Figure 4 b).

Prony parameters for matrix			
Branch	K_{eq} [GPa]	K_1 [MPa]	τ_1 [s]
1	2.5	119.54	108.92

Table 2: Prony parameter obtained through fitting the experimental data of the unreinforced material PBT.

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

This section presents the motivation for employing the probability modeling approach to model spatially distributed mechanical properties. The experimental findings are presented at the microscale and component level of PBT and PBT GF30. This is achieved through a tensile creep test at the component level and nanoindentation at the microscale.

3.1 Materials used in composite

In this comprehensive experimental investigation, a standardized tensile test specimen is utilized, which is directly molded with reinforced fibers (PBT GF30) and without fibers (PBT). The matrix material is a thermoplastic Polybutylene Terephthalate, representing the primary component, which is marketed under the trade name ULTRADUR B 4520 by BASF. The reinforcing component of the composite is E-Glass, designated as FGCS 3540 and provided by STW. The manufacturing of all specimens was carried out using an injection molding process at Kunststoff-Zentrum Leipzig GmbH.

3.2 Experimental setup and specimen preparation

3.2.1 Investigation at the microscale

For the experimental investigation at the microscale, a ZHN nanoindenter from ZwickRoell, equipped with a Berkovich indenter, was used. To do this, a small specimen is removed from the tensile test sample, as illustrated in Figure 5. The extracted specimen was prepared by grinding and polishing, as detailed in [4]. The nanoindentation tests are performed with a force of 1750 mN and a hold phase of 300 s. The creep value Cr represents the viscoelastic property and is expressed as

$$\text{Creep} = Cr = h_2 - h_1, \tag{16}$$

where h_2 and h_1 are the maximum depth of the indentation test and the beginning of the holding phase, respectively, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: A small sample is extracted from the tensile test specimen. The gray marked surface is of interest for the indentation test.

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the nanoindentation curve derived from the indentation test. This includes an example of the nanoindentation test procedure, illustrating the search for the contact point, the beginning of the hold phase at h_1 , and the end of the hold phase at h_2 .

3.2.2 Investigation at the Component level

For the experimental investigation at the component level, the specimen is divided into $L = 15$ areas, each with an initial length of 5 mm, as depicted in Figure 7. Creep behavior in these areas is measured using the ARAMIS 3D digital image correlation system. Consequently, the assessment of creep behavior is conducted within these designated areas, allowing for the determination of its local distribution across the specimen. A detailed description of this experimental setup and conditions can be found in [5].

Figure 7: Tensile test specimens were divided into 15 areas with an initial length of 5 mm to measure local viscoelasticity properties.

3.3 Experimental results and validation

3.3.1 Experimental results at the microscale

To evaluate the variations in microscale viscoelastic behavior, nanoindentation measurements were conducted across the specimen's cross-section, as shown in Figure 5 and 6. The distribution of creep values is displayed in Figure 8. For PBT, the unreinforced matrix exhibits a fairly uniform response. In contrast, PBT GF30 exhibits significant variability in microscale viscoelastic behavior, indicating microstructural heterogeneity resulting from the embedded short fibers.

(a) PBT

(b) PBT GF30

Figure 8: Creep value Cr of 160 measurement points over the cross-section, a) represents the unreinforced material PBT, and b) the short fiber-reinforced material PBT GF30.

3.3.2 Experimental results and validation at the component level

This microscale trend is also observed at the component level, as demonstrated in Figure 9, which illustrates the distribution of the viscoelastic parameter K_i . In that figure, the local distribution of K_i , as introduced in Equation 3, is presented. This distribution is derived from the Prony series after five

minutes of creep testing for both PBT and PBT GF30 using the Levenberg-Marquardt method. The unreinforced PBT specimen shows a relatively uniform distribution of K_i values. Conversely, the PBT GF30 specimen exhibits a substantial increase in scatter, indicative of considerable spatial variability resulting from the limited fiber reinforcement.

Figure 9: The local distribution at the component level for one specimen, as introduced in Figure 3, shows the Prony parameter K_i obtained by fitting Equation 3 using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. The global mean value is obtained experimentally over a length of 75 mm and represents 20 specimens.

Finally, Figure 10 b) presents a comparison between the experimental creep data and the numerically predicted results obtained using the Karhunen-Loève based stochastic modeling approach. The close agreement observed demonstrates the model's ability to accurately capture the spatially varying viscoelastic behavior of the fiber-reinforced composite. The 15 areas introduced in Figure 7 at the component level are illustrated here, aligning with both the experimental and numerical data.

Figure 10: Numerical results include a) numerical results of $C_{11}^{\delta}(t)$ of the time-dependent at five different artificial microstructures, and b) a comparison between experimental creep data and numerical results modeled using the Karhunen-Loève approach, all 15 areas are shown.

4 CONCLUSION

The experimental investigations on both the component level and microscale demonstrate that the presence and distribution of short fibers significantly influence the spatial distribution of viscoelastic properties. The obtained results clearly indicate the need for a probabilistic modeling approach to accurately capture the behavior of the distributed mechanical properties. In this context, the Karhunen-Loève expansion is a suitable method that offers a compact and efficient representation of second-order Gaussian random fields. The numerical results derived from this approach demonstrate strong agreement with the experimental data, providing further validation of its applicability.

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